

Supplemental table 1. List of differentially expressed genes (p-value<0.001) and their abundance (log CPM) in response to the gene knock-down with default log-fold change thresholds of -1 and 1

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
DUSP1	ACHE	1.35	3.55
DUSP1	ANO5	2.33	2.34
DUSP1	CD34	-1.41	3.01
DUSP1	CXCL12	-1.10	4.98
DUSP1	DUSP1	-1.04	5.46
DUSP1	FABP7	1.17	5.36
DUSP1	FBN2	1.02	2.81
DUSP1	HAPLN1	1.97	1.64
DUSP1	KCNG1	1.10	2.03
DUSP1	KCNK3	1.15	3.14
DUSP1	LY6G5B	-1.39	1.59
DUSP1	MCM2	1.22	2.00
DUSP1	PCDHB12	2.05	0.55
DUSP1	PLA2G2A	1.12	6.44
DUSP1	SEZ6L2	1.11	2.59
DUSP1	SNORA70G	-1.06	2.46
DUSP1	SPARCL1	-1.51	2.24
DUSP1	SPATA31C1	-2.25	2.11
DUSP1	TNC	1.44	3.18
DUSP1	TPRG1	1.47	2.70
DUSP1	TRIM16L	-1.12	2.33
DUSP1	TSPAN18	-1.33	2.02
SIK1	C10orf91	1.12	2.26
SIK1	C12orf75	-1.05	5.10
SIK1	CRYAB	-1.01	8.56
SIK1	FABP3	-1.49	5.00
SIK1	IER5L	-1.45	2.49
SIK1	IGFBP6	-1.18	6.07
SIK1	LOC645638	-1.73	3.11
SIK1	MYADM	-1.07	3.63
SIK1	OLFML2A	-1.85	1.74
SIK1	PCDHB12	2.51	0.55
SIK1	PHKG2	-1.84	1.01
SIK1	PHLDA2	-1.14	3.31
SIK1	RPL23AP82	-1.30	2.56
SIK1	S100A4	-1.33	8.07
SIK1	SEMA7A	-1.12	3.27
SIK1	SLC16A13	-1.32	2.04
SIK1	SLC6A6	-1.61	2.64
SIK1	SLC7A11	-1.01	3.61
SIK1	SPATA31C1	-3.16	2.11
SIK1	TRIM16L	-1.37	2.33
SIK1	ZNF493	-1.40	2.55
SIK1	ZNF542	-1.24	3.74
SOCS3	ABCA8	-1.82	2.47

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	ABCC1	-1.13	4.08
SOCS3	ACHE	1.32	3.55
SOCS3	ACSF2	1.19	7.61
SOCS3	ADAMTS5	-1.25	5.49
SOCS3	ADAP1	-1.23	2.12
SOCS3	ADCY1	2.11	1.00
SOCS3	ADH1B	1.08	10.06
SOCS3	AEBP1	-1.02	4.74
SOCS3	AGTR1	-2.60	0.56
SOCS3	AHNAK	-1.35	4.05
SOCS3	AHR	-1.90	3.53
SOCS3	AJUBA	-1.79	2.21
SOCS3	AKAP12	-1.27	4.13
SOCS3	ALCAM	-1.44	4.22
SOCS3	ALDH1B1	-1.01	4.04
SOCS3	ALDH3B2	1.23	2.65
SOCS3	ALYREF	-1.03	4.62
SOCS3	ANO5	3.76	2.34
SOCS3	AP4B1	-1.04	3.66
SOCS3	ARMCX3	-1.08	3.69
SOCS3	ASAP3	-1.28	2.85
SOCS3	ASPHD1	1.94	1.66
SOCS3	ASPN	-3.15	1.95
SOCS3	ATN1	-1.14	7.28
SOCS3	AUTS2	-1.59	1.33
SOCS3	B2M	1.06	9.67
SOCS3	B9D1	1.03	5.32
SOCS3	BHLHE40	1.24	4.02
SOCS3	BMP6	-1.75	1.52
SOCS3	C10orf11	1.37	1.56
SOCS3	C16orf89	1.17	3.10
SOCS3	C1orf115	-1.38	1.44
SOCS3	C1orf21	-1.05	3.57
SOCS3	C2orf68	-1.04	2.62
SOCS3	C3orf55	1.20	1.78
SOCS3	C6orf132	-3.40	0.29
SOCS3	C6orf70	1.18	3.57
SOCS3	CADPS2	1.36	2.58
SOCS3	CAPN2	-1.31	4.95
SOCS3	CASO2	1.04	3.24
SOCS3	CCDC102A	-2.28	0.74
SOCS3	CCDC80	-1.02	3.67
SOCS3	CCRN4L	-1.32	2.47
SOCS3	CD34	-2.60	3.01
SOCS3	CDK6	-1.02	4.18
SOCS3	CDR2L	-1.08	2.21
SOCS3	CES1	1.15	4.51
SOCS3	CFHR1	-2.81	2.78
SOCS3	CFI	2.26	1.66

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	CGREF1	1.41	3.60
SOCS3	CHI3L1	2.52	4.17
SOCS3	CHI3L2	1.44	12.10
SOCS3	CHST8	1.78	3.36
SOCS3	CIDEA	3.33	-0.01
SOCS3	CITED1	1.37	1.95
SOCS3	CKMT1A	1.84	3.84
SOCS3	CKMT1B	2.57	5.52
SOCS3	CKMT2	1.13	7.96
SOCS3	CLCN6	-1.05	3.69
SOCS3	CLDN23	1.02	3.24
SOCS3	CLEC3B	-4.19	5.30
SOCS3	CLIC2	1.10	2.59
SOCS3	COL1A1	-1.08	10.87
SOCS3	COMMD8	1.00	3.44
SOCS3	COO3	1.22	3.18
SOCS3	CPA4	-1.90	1.39
SOCS3	CPEB1	1.33	2.93
SOCS3	CPT1B	1.45	5.49
SOCS3	CRABP2	-1.12	7.13
SOCS3	CRIP1	-2.77	2.74
SOCS3	CRLF1	-2.97	4.41
SOCS3	CTBP2	-1.20	4.78
SOCS3	CTDSPL2	-1.44	3.04
SOCS3	CTGF	-1.14	7.21
SOCS3	CTTN	-1.01	5.94
SOCS3	CYGB	1.15	5.52
SOCS3	CYR61	-1.05	5.96
SOCS3	DAB1	-4.14	0.19
SOCS3	DBN1	-1.45	5.70
SOCS3	DDR1	-1.29	2.30
SOCS3	DEFB1	2.72	1.49
SOCS3	DKK2	-2.10	1.63
SOCS3	DPT	-1.14	5.48
SOCS3	EBF2	-1.38	2.85
SOCS3	EBF3	-1.07	3.30
SOCS3	EGR1	-1.96	3.92
SOCS3	EHD2	-1.04	7.06
SOCS3	ELN	-1.23	5.89
SOCS3	ELP5	1.12	5.98
SOCS3	EMILIN2	-1.28	2.05
SOCS3	ENOPH1	1.13	5.13
SOCS3	EPAS1	-1.08	7.08
SOCS3	EPHA2	-2.51	1.43
SOCS3	EPHX2	2.08	0.72
SOCS3	ERBB2	-1.45	2.65
SOCS3	F10	-1.78	1.58
SOCS3	F2RL2	-1.50	2.07
SOCS3	FABP7	2.71	5.36

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	FAM102B	-1.57	2.13
SOCS3	FAM108C1	-1.68	1.33
SOCS3	FAM111A	-1.00	2.66
SOCS3	FAM114A1	-1.06	5.08
SOCS3	FAM131B	-1.73	1.45
SOCS3	FAM168A	-1.22	3.03
SOCS3	FAM26E	-1.29	1.85
SOCS3	FASTKD3	1.01	4.48
SOCS3	FBN1	-1.30	7.41
SOCS3	FCN1	1.60	3.41
SOCS3	FGL2	-1.83	2.03
SOCS3	FHIT	1.34	3.69
SOCS3	FKBP9	-1.07	6.40
SOCS3	FLJ35024	1.44	2.17
SOCS3	FLNC	-1.19	5.90
SOCS3	FLRT2	-1.89	1.63
SOCS3	FLT3LG	-1.44	1.68
SOCS3	FMO1	3.08	2.38
SOCS3	FMO4	1.37	1.56
SOCS3	FONG	1.87	2.75
SOCS3	FOXC2	-2.42	0.70
SOCS3	FOXN2	-1.09	3.56
SOCS3	FOXP2	1.31	2.17
SOCS3	FRY	-1.35	1.90
SOCS3	FST	-1.04	3.55
SOCS3	FSTL1	-1.36	8.82
SOCS3	GALNTL1	-1.47	2.34
SOCS3	GARS	-1.03	6.47
SOCS3	GEM	-1.28	3.30
SOCS3	GLI2	-1.69	1.16
SOCS3	GNG2	-1.07	5.77
SOCS3	GPC1	-1.28	5.80
SOCS3	GPX3	-1.03	2.97
SOCS3	GRIA3	-2.06	3.40
SOCS3	GRIN2D	-1.47	1.44
SOCS3	GRK5	-1.39	2.24
SOCS3	GSN	-1.30	6.97
SOCS3	H19	-1.44	9.41
SOCS3	HGD	-2.75	1.24
SOCS3	HLA-B	1.31	5.94
SOCS3	HMCN1	1.27	1.61
SOCS3	HNRNPH1	-1.02	4.39
SOCS3	HP	1.15	6.70
SOCS3	HSPA1B	-1.15	4.72
SOCS3	HSPB7	-1.43	3.72
SOCS3	IGFBP2	1.49	5.13
SOCS3	IGFBP6	-1.50	6.07
SOCS3	IGSF10	-1.28	2.91
SOCS3	INHBB	-1.82	1.73

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	ITGA11	-1.24	3.98
SOCS3	ITGA8	-2.34	0.77
SOCS3	ITGBL1	-1.29	4.36
SOCS3	ITPRIPL2	-1.45	4.07
SOCS3	KAZALD1	-2.01	2.39
SOCS3	KCNK3	1.10	3.14
SOCS3	KIAA1462	1.06	3.87
SOCS3	KIAA2026	-1.27	2.64
SOCS3	KITLG	-1.24	3.02
SOCS3	KLF12	-1.47	2.23
SOCS3	KLF2	-1.39	3.30
SOCS3	KLHDC10	-1.02	4.36
SOCS3	KLHL10	1.53	1.41
SOCS3	KRT8	-1.65	1.08
SOCS3	LBH	-1.47	2.20
SOCS3	LDB2	-1.65	2.15
SOCS3	LEP	-2.50	1.33
SOCS3	LEPR	-1.47	3.19
SOCS3	LIMS2	-1.97	1.72
SOCS3	LIMS3L	1.41	0.86
SOCS3	LINC00284	1.89	1.25
SOCS3	LMO7	-1.10	2.78
SOCS3	LMOD1	-3.43	0.91
SOCS3	LOC100130872	1.16	4.09
SOCS3	LOC100133985	1.49	2.01
SOCS3	LOC100505633	-2.04	4.46
SOCS3	LOX	-1.55	6.75
SOCS3	LOXL1	-1.24	5.69
SOCS3	LRFN5	-1.48	1.81
SOCS3	LTBP1	-1.61	2.14
SOCS3	LTBP4	-1.57	1.04
SOCS3	MAN2A2	-1.08	4.95
SOCS3	MAP1B	-1.23	5.45
SOCS3	MAP1LC3B2	1.04	7.02
SOCS3	MAP7	1.19	3.19
SOCS3	MAPK7	-1.09	3.41
SOCS3	MAPK8IP2	1.35	3.52
SOCS3	MARCKS	-1.70	5.29
SOCS3	MBOAT2	-1.88	1.47
SOCS3	MDH1	1.08	7.82
SOCS3	MEDAG	-1.20	3.11
SOCS3	MEGF8	-1.02	2.93
SOCS3	MFAP5	-1.73	7.28
SOCS3	MFSD6	-1.72	1.12
SOCS3	MIDN	-1.16	3.01
SOCS3	MLL3	-1.09	2.90
SOCS3	MMP1	1.97	1.21
SOCS3	MRPL46	1.12	8.16
SOCS3	MSRB3	-1.05	4.34

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	MTA1	-1.10	4.76
SOCS3	MX1	2.60	0.83
SOCS3	NAMPT	1.02	8.35
SOCS3	NAV3	-1.11	3.57
SOCS3	NCALD	-1.22	2.09
SOCS3	NCOR1	-1.19	3.90
SOCS3	NDNF	-3.57	1.38
SOCS3	NDUFA4L2	-1.35	2.76
SOCS3	NEDD9	-1.20	2.58
SOCS3	NEGR1	-1.96	1.26
SOCS3	NEIL2	-1.70	1.22
SOCS3	NOP10	1.06	9.80
SOCS3	NOTCH3	-1.97	4.37
SOCS3	NOTO	1.04	4.31
SOCS3	NPC1L1	2.03	0.69
SOCS3	NOO1	-1.18	7.35
SOCS3	NT5DC1	1.02	4.39
SOCS3	NTN4	-1.52	3.04
SOCS3	OAS1	1.05	4.23
SOCS3	OLFML3	-1.04	3.04
SOCS3	OTUD3	-1.38	2.33
SOCS3	P2RX6	1.08	3.76
SOCS3	PACRG	2.09	1.14
SOCS3	PAMR1	-1.10	3.36
SOCS3	PCDHGA10	-1.21	2.79
SOCS3	PCDHGA2	-1.49	2.08
SOCS3	PCDHGB6	-1.37	1.69
SOCS3	PCDHGC3	-1.38	3.47
SOCS3	PCOLCE	-1.10	7.89
SOCS3	PCSK1	1.07	2.66
SOCS3	PEX11A	1.04	4.84
SOCS3	PFKFB2	1.07	3.20
SOCS3	PHGDH	-1.43	5.14
SOCS3	PLA2G2A	2.44	6.44
SOCS3	PLAC9	-1.94	6.16
SOCS3	PLK1S1	1.16	2.53
SOCS3	PNKD	1.07	2.83
SOCS3	PRKAG2-AS1	1.03	3.36
SOCS3	PRKD1	-1.35	2.47
SOCS3	PSMB8	1.15	3.29
SOCS3	PTBP2	-1.70	1.60
SOCS3	PTCD3	1.04	6.46
SOCS3	PTCH1	-2.02	0.76
SOCS3	PTGER2	-1.08	2.68
SOCS3	PTGER4	-2.11	0.71
SOCS3	PTGIS	-2.35	1.96
SOCS3	PTGR1	-1.31	4.69
SOCS3	PTK2B	1.07	5.99
SOCS3	PTPN14	-1.13	2.88

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	PTX3	-1.60	7.06
SOCS3	RAB3D	-1.15	2.64
SOCS3	RAB3GAP2	-1.43	3.50
SOCS3	RAB42	1.05	4.25
SOCS3	RAP2B	-1.44	4.46
SOCS3	RAPH1	-1.54	2.90
SOCS3	RARG	-1.14	2.15
SOCS3	RASSF2	-1.73	1.43
SOCS3	RASSF9	-1.84	0.96
SOCS3	RBP1	1.71	2.70
SOCS3	RBP7	1.19	1.92
SOCS3	RHOBTB1	-1.17	1.99
SOCS3	RHOJ	-1.22	2.56
SOCS3	RNF152	-1.41	1.87
SOCS3	RNF24	-1.34	1.57
SOCS3	ROR1	-1.34	3.82
SOCS3	RPL23AP32	-1.32	3.42
SOCS3	RPL29P2	-1.36	1.21
SOCS3	RPS6KA2	-1.23	3.50
SOCS3	RRAGD	2.47	2.92
SOCS3	S100A10	-1.11	5.66
SOCS3	S100A4	-1.43	8.07
SOCS3	S100P	1.51	2.76
SOCS3	S1PR3	-2.28	1.67
SOCS3	SBSN	2.48	0.17
SOCS3	SCN8A	-1.91	1.14
SOCS3	SCRG1	-2.38	3.16
SOCS3	SEMA3B	-1.51	1.32
SOCS3	SEMA3D	-2.05	2.34
SOCS3	SERPINA3	1.83	1.23
SOCS3	SERPINB2	-3.39	1.61
SOCS3	SEZ6L2	2.05	2.59
SOCS3	SFRP1	-1.87	6.05
SOCS3	SFRP2	2.09	2.38
SOCS3	SGK3	-1.22	2.19
SOCS3	SH3D19	-1.27	5.26
SOCS3	SHOX2	-1.61	1.38
SOCS3	SIM1	-1.39	3.98
SOCS3	SKP2	-1.25	3.01
SOCS3	SLC16A13	-1.08	2.04
SOCS3	SLC19A3	1.10	4.93
SOCS3	SLC22A12	1.29	2.69
SOCS3	SLC44A2	-1.34	2.84
SOCS3	SLC47A1	3.05	1.11
SOCS3	SLC5A6	1.35	7.57
SOCS3	SLC7A11	-1.52	3.61
SOCS3	SMO	1.36	2.34
SOCS3	SNAI2	-1.54	4.81
SOCS3	SNORA14B	-1.85	2.03

Knock-Down	Gene Symbol	log (Fold Change)	log (CPM)
SOCS3	SOX4	-1.21	3.88
SOCS3	SPARCL1	-1.85	2.24
SOCS3	SRGAP1	-1.28	2.37
SOCS3	SRGN	-2.14	2.71
SOCS3	SRPX	-1.52	6.53
SOCS3	ST6GALNAC5	1.58	1.82
SOCS3	STC1	-1.03	3.60
SOCS3	STEAP4	3.22	0.28
SOCS3	STK32C	1.01	5.50
SOCS3	STMN2	-1.66	1.78
SOCS3	SVEP1	-2.18	4.08
SOCS3	SYDE1	-1.02	4.46
SOCS3	SYNDIG1	1.29	3.46
SOCS3	TAGLN	-1.50	6.88
SOCS3	TBX2	-1.24	2.76
SOCS3	TCF21	-2.51	1.30
SOCS3	TES	-1.11	3.15
SOCS3	TET1	-1.51	1.86
SOCS3	TFEB	1.38	1.86
SOCS3	TGFB2	-1.15	3.93
SOCS3	THEMIS2	1.09	2.78
SOCS3	TIFA	1.13	2.15
SOCS3	TM4SF1	-1.12	4.86
SOCS3	TMEM140	1.04	5.36
SOCS3	TMEM59L	-2.58	0.77
SOCS3	TMSB4X	-1.20	10.21
SOCS3	TNC	2.34	3.18
SOCS3	TNFAIP2	-1.39	2.69
SOCS3	TNFAIP8	-1.56	2.22
SOCS3	TNXA	-3.24	0.66
SOCS3	TNXB	-2.47	2.63
SOCS3	TPRG1	1.33	2.70
SOCS3	TRNP1	-1.96	3.09
SOCS3	TRPV2	-1.38	2.26
SOCS3	TSPAN18	-2.46	2.02
SOCS3	UCP1	1.37	5.04
SOCS3	WISP2	2.04	1.65
SOCS3	YWHAG	-1.04	7.82
SOCS3	ZFPM2	-1.42	3.25
SOCS3	ZNF337	-1.56	1.41
SOCS3	ZNF460	-1.16	3.86
SOCS3	ZNF81	-1.32	2.19
SOCS3	ZP1	1.60	0.94
SOCS3	ZXDC	-1.52	3.54
SOCS3	ZYX	-1.20	6.87

Supplemental Table 2. List of up- and down-regulated differentially expressed genes in response to the gene knock-down included in the Gene Ontology (GO) biological process enrichment analysis.

Knock-Down	GO:Biological Process	Description	DEGs included	q-value	Regulation
DUSP1	GO:0050900	leukocyte migration	CD34/DUSP1/CXCL12	0.0074493	Down-regulated
DUSP1	GO:0001649	osteoblast differentiation	TNC/ACHE/FBN2	0.0302103	Up-regulated
DUSP1	GO:0001503	ossification	TNC/ACHE/FBN2	0.0388249	Up-regulated
DUSP1	GO:0050808	synapse organization	TNC/SEZ6L2/ACHE	0.0388249	Up-regulated
SIK1	GO:0098657	import into cell	SLC7A11/SLC6A6/FABP3	0.0360488	Down-regulated
SIK1	GO:0046942	carboxylic acid transport	SLC7A11/SLC16A13/SLC6A6	0.0360488	Down-regulated
SIK1	GO:0015849	organic acid transport	SLC7A11/SLC6A6/FABP3	0.0360488	Down-regulated
SIK1	GO:0062012	regulation of small molecule metabolic process	SLC7A11/PHKG2/FABP3	0.0360488	Down-regulated
SIK1	GO:0015711	organic anion transport	SLC7A11/SLC16A13/SLC6A6	0.0397867	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001503	ossification	CLEC3B/SFRP1/LOX/SNAI2/ASPN/SRGN/EPHA2/TGFB2/COL1A1/CDK6/LEP/KAZALD1/ITGA11/IGSF10/ALYREF/PTGER4/RASSF2/GLI2/STC1/PTCH1/SHOX2/FOXC2/PRKD1/BMP6	0.0000001	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0030198	extracellular matrix organization	LOX/PTX3/ADAMTS5/NTN4/TNXB/LOXL1/NDNF/TGFB2/TNXA/FLRT2/ELN/COL1A1/KAZALD1/AEBP1/DPT/ITGA8/DDR1/CCDC80/FOXC2	0.0000013	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0043062	extracellular structure organization	LOX/PTX3/ADAMTS5/NTN4/TNXB/LOXL1/NDNF/TGFB2/TNXA/FLRT2/ELN/COL1A1/KAZALD1/AEBP1/DPT/ITGA8/DDR1/CCDC80/FOXC2	0.0000013	Down-regulated

Knock-Down	GO:Biological Process	Description	DEGs included	q-value	Regulation
SOCS3	GO:0045229	external encapsulating structure organization	LOX/PTX3/ADAMTS5/NTN4/ TNXB/LOXL1/NDNF/TGFB2/ TNXA/FLRT2/ELN/COL1A1/ KAZALD1/AEBP1/DPT/ITGA8/ DDR1/CCDC80/FOXC2	0.0000013	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001655	urogenital system development	CRLF1/SFRP1/EGR1/FBN1/ NOTCH3/SIM1/CD34/CRIP1/ TGFB2/TMEM59L/SOX4/TCF21/ ITGA8/AGTR1/GLI2/RARG/PTCH1/ FOXC2/BMP6	0.0000067	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0030199	collagen fibril organization	LOX/TNXB/LOXL1/TGFB2/TNXA/ COL1A1/AEBP1/DPT/FOXC2	0.0000111	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0060560	developmental growth involved in morphogenesis	SFRP1/DBN1/ALCAM/MAP1B/ SEMA3D/RAPH1/CRABP2/CTTN/ TBX2/TRPV2/DDR1/MEGF8/RARG/ SEMA3B/AUTS2	0.0000129	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001822	kidney development	CRLF1/SFRP1/EGR1/FBN1/ NOTCH3/SIM1/CD34/TGFB2/ TMEM59L/SOX4/TCF21/ITGA8/ AGTR1/GLI2/PTCH1/FOXC2/BMP6	0.0000137	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0072001	renal system development	CRLF1/SFRP1/EGR1/FBN1/ NOTCH3/SIM1/CD34/TGFB2/ TMEM59L/SOX4/TCF21/ITGA8/ AGTR1/GLI2/PTCH1/FOXC2/BMP6	0.0000185	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0016049	cell growth	SFRP1/DBN1/ALCAM/MAP1B/ TGFB2/SEMA3D/RAPH1/CRABP2/ CTTN/TRPV2/KAZALD1/DDR1/ ERBB2/MEGF8/AGTR1/HSPA1B/ RARG/SGK3/SEMA3B/AUTS2/ LTBP4	0.0000209	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0022612	gland morphogenesis	SFRP1/SNAI2/NTN4/CRIP1/EPHA2/ TGFB2/TBX2/LIMS2/DDR1/RARG/ PTCH1	0.0000209	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0031589	cell-substrate adhesion	SFRP1/ZYX/CD34/NTN4/TNXB/ NDNF/ITGBL1/CTTN/S100A10/ AJUBA/COL1A1/LIMS2/CDK6/ ITGA11/ITGA8/DDR1/NEDD9/ CCDC80	0.0000224	Down-regulated

Knock-Down	GO:Biological Process	Description	DEGs included	q-value	Regulation
SOCS3	GO:0007409	axonogenesis	DBN1/NOTCH3/ALCAM/MAP1B/ EPHA2/SEMA3D/RAPH1/CRABP2/ FLRT2/CTTN/TRPV2/ERBB2/ MEGF8/DAB1/GLI2/PTCH1/ SEMA3B/SHOX2/AUTS2	0.0000560	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0061564	axon development	DBN1/NOTCH3/ALCAM/MAP1B/ EPHA2/SEMA3D/RAPH1/CRABP2/ FLRT2/CTTN/TRPV2/DDR1/ ERBB2/MEGF8/DAB1/GLI2/PTCH1/ SEMA3B/SHOX2/AUTS2	0.0000658	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0033627	cell adhesion mediated by integrin	FBN1/SNAI2/EPHA2/TGFB2/ ITGBL1/ITGA11/ITGA8/FOXC2/ EMILIN2	0.0000733	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001649	osteoblast differentiation	SFRP1/LOX/SNAI2/EPHA2/ COL1A1/CDK6/ITGA11/ALYREF/ RASSF2/GLI2/PTCH1/SHOX2/ PRKD1/BMP6	0.0000733	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0048675	axon extension	DBN1/ALCAM/MAP1B/SEMA3D/ RAPH1/CTTN/TRPV2/MEGF8/ SEMA3B/AUTS2	0.0001180	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0007178	transmembrane receptor protein serine/threonine kinase signaling pathway	SFRP1/LOX/FSTL1/EGR1/FBN1/ ZYG1/ASP1/TGFB2/FST/LTBP1/ INHBB/ITGA8/TET1/CTDSPL2/ MEGF8/LTBP4/BMP6	0.0001634	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0048588	developmental cell growth	DBN1/ALCAM/MAP1B/SEMA3D/ RAPH1/CRABP2/CTTN/TRPV2/ DDR1/MEGF8/RARG/SEMA3B/ AUTS2	0.0001643	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0061448	connective tissue development	LOX/EGR1/SNAI2/CD34/CRIP1/ COL1A1/LEP/EBF2/MBOAT2/ RARG/STC1/SHOX2/FOXC2/BMP6	0.0002118	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001763	morphogenesis of a branching structure	SFRP1/SNAI2/NTN4/EPHA2/ TMEM59L/TBX2/TCF21/DDR1/ GLI2/PTCH1/SHOX2/FOXC2	0.0002521	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:1990138	neuron projection extension	DBN1/ALCAM/MAP1B/SEMA3D/ RAPH1/CTTN/TRPV2/DDR1/ MEGF8/SEMA3B/AUTS2	0.0003010	Down-regulated

Knock-Down	GO:Biological Process	Description	DEGs included	q-value	Regulation
SOCS3	GO:0090092	regulation of transmembrane receptor protein serine/threonine kinase signaling pathway	SFRP1/LOX/FSTL1/FBN1/ASPEN/ TGFB2/FST/LTBP1/INHBB/ITGA8/ TET1/CTDSPL2/LTBP4/BMP6	0.0003556	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0001558	regulation of cell growth	SFRP1/DBN1/MAP1B/TGFB2/ SEMA3D/CRABP2/CTTN/TRPV2/ KAZALD1/DDR1/ERBB2/MEGF8/ AGTR1/HSPA1B/SGK3/SEMA3B/ LTBP4	0.0003556	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:1902903	regulation of supramolecular fiber organization	SFRP1/GSN/DBN1/TNXB/MAP1B/ TMSB4X/LMOD1/NAV3/CTTN/ S100A10/ELN/STMN2/AEBP1/ ASAP3/PTGER4/HSPA1B	0.0004358	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0048608	reproductive structure development	SFRP1/PTX3/ATN1/CRIP1/TGFB2/ ZFPM2/FST/KITLG/TCF21/LEP/ INHBB/RARG/PTCH1/BMP6	0.0005594	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0061138	morphogenesis of a branching epithelium	SFRP1/SNAI2/NTN4/EPHA2/ TMEM59L/TBX2/TCF21/DDR1/ GLI2/PTCH1/FOXC2	0.0005594	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0042060	wound healing	LOX/CD34/SERPINB2/NDNF/ TGFB2/SLC7A11/AHNAK/ S100A10/AJUBA/RAP2B/COL1A1/ F10/DDR1/F2RL2/ERBB2/FOXC2/ EMILIN2	0.0005594	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0030522	intracellular receptor signaling pathway	SFRP1/SNAI2/AHR/CTBP2/PTGIS/ TCF21/LEP/NCOR1/LBH/SKP2/ KLF2/HSPA1B/RARG	0.0005594	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0061458	reproductive system development	SFRP1/PTX3/ATN1/CRIP1/TGFB2/ ZFPM2/FST/KITLG/TCF21/LEP/ INHBB/RARG/PTCH1/BMP6	0.0005892	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0048568	embryonic organ development	MFAP5/FBN1/EPHA2/TGFB2/ ZFPM2/EPAS1/TBX2/KITLG/TCF21/ ITGA8/MEGF8/GLI2/RARG/PTCH1/ FLT3LG/SHOX2/FOXC2	0.0006196	Down-regulated
SOCS3	GO:0071560	cellular response to transforming	CLEC3B/SFRP1/LOX/FBN1/ZYX/ ASPEN/TGFB2/MAPK7/LTBP1/	0.0006196	Down-regulated

Knock-Down	GO:Biological Process	Description	DEGs included	q-value	Regulation
		growth factor beta stimulus	COL1A1/ITGA8/TET1/LTBP4		
SOCS3	GO:0071559	response to transforming growth factor beta	CLEC3B/SFRP1/LOX/FBN1/ZYX/ ASPN/TGFB2/MAPK7/LTBP1/ COL1A1/ITGA8/TET1/LTBP4	0.0007597	Down-regulated

A minimum size of three genes was used for the functional enrichment. Biological processes with q-value < 0.05 were considered enriched.